

ALUMNI Community
Photo Album

NEMO
ALUMNI
EST. 2014

NEMO Summer School Series

powered by **Open | Models
Laboratory**

Editor

OMiLAB gGmbH (NPO)

DOI

10.5281/zenodo.12580915

Imprint

Media Owner and Publisher

OMiLAB gGmbH (NPO)

Picture Rights

All logos used in the brochure are property of their respective owners.

Illustrations, Graphics, Icons & other photos: Pixabay, Designed by Freepik, Private Archive, OMiLAB NPO.

NEMO ALUMNI Community

- Hard Facts -

 Participants: 575

 Countries: 54

 Nationalities: 73

 Institutions: 187

Est. 2014

1st Edition - NEMO 2014 Summer School

NEMO 2014

Alpen-Adria Universität Klagenfurt, Austria
06th - 19th of July 2014

The PARTICIPANTS

Jakhongir Ashrapov

Fatma Aydemir

Marzieh Bakhshandeh

Björn Benner

Bogdan Fleaca

Vogler Sandro

Uma Srithar

Nikolaos Tantouris

Tina Morawek

Renata Vaderna

Erol Valeriu Chioasca

Yeonbok Choe

WooRim Choi

Riccardo Cognini

Aikaterini Dimitraki

Maria Carolina Valverde Corrado

Željko Vuković

Maedeh Yassae

Christos Zepenoglou

Vladimir Dimitrieski

Vojislav Djukic

Dominik Jung

Milorad Filipović

Hector Arturo Florenz Fernandez

Laima Genava

Filippos Gouidis

Farideh Heidari

Željko Ivković

Jeroen De Koninck

Panagiotis Karantzias

Orestis Koufogiannidis

Emanuele Laurenzi

Keletso Joel Letsholo

Feng-Lin Li

Tong Li

Thomas Luft

Natalia Parrado Cepeda

Ari Peltoniemi

Tatiana Poletaeva

Nithyanandrasa Prashanthan

Robert Eikermann

Ben Roelens

Alicja Rogowska

Marcela Ruiz

<https://nemo.omilab.org/2014/>

Participants: 44

Nationalities: 21

Institutions: 25

Countries: 15

2nd Edition - NEMO 2015 Summer School

2nd Edition in the NEMO Summer School Series
NEXT GENERATION ENTERPRISE MODELLING
July 20th - July 31st, 2015
University of Vienna, Austria
www.omlab.org/camp2015

universität wien OMLAB ALPEN-ADRIA UNIVERSITÄT ERASMUS+

NEMO Summer School Series
The NEMO summer schools focus on the conceptualization, design, and implementation of Next Generation Enterprise Modelling Methods.
In today's enterprises, modelling methods are widely used on every level and they are mostly supported by modelling tools. These tools ease the design of machine-processable models and provide facility services, e.g. for accessing, exchanging and persistently storing meta-models and models, for applying algorithms and querying model contents. Additionally they enhance the value of models as an organizational knowledge platform.
Modelling tools and platforms which support domain specific methods used to provide user interaction functionalities and enable management capabilities for the execution environment in addition to the modelling method design and implementation.

Framework and Topics
The generic modelling method framework proposed by Karagiannis and Kühn (2001) comprises all the necessary ingredients for the conceptualization, i.e. early development and prototyping phases of modelling tools for domain specific modelling methods.
The framework addresses (a) modelling languages - syntax, semantic and notation, (b) modelling procedures and (c) processing based on their mechanisms and algorithms.
The summer school provides a highly-interactive experimental environment, where students and teachers focus on modelling addressing especially:
• Foundations of Conceptual Modelling
• Technologies for Conceptual Modelling
• Applications Domains
• Cross-cutting issues.

Contributing Lecturers and Institutions

Prof. Dr. Xavier Boucher	Dr. Manfred Jeusfeld	Prof. Dr. Heinrich C. Mayr	Prof. Dr. Peter Reimann
Dr. Robert Buchmann	Prof. Dr. Dimitris Karagiannis	Prof. Dr. John Mylopoulos	Prof. Dr. Ulrich Reimer
Prof. Dr. Luis Camarinha-Matos	Prof. Dr. Marite Kirikova	Prof. Dr. Andreas Oberweis	Prof. Dr. Wolfgang Reising
Prof. Dr. Elisabetta di Nitto	Prof. Dr. John Krogsette	Prof. Dr. Oscar Pastor	Prof. Dr. Matti Rossi
PD Dr. Hans-Georg Pill	Prof. Dr. Moon Kwon Lee	Prof. Dr. Dimitris Pissinakis	Prof. Dr. Brian Selic
Prof. Dr. Ulrich Frank	Prof. Dr. Pericles Loucopoulos	Prof. Dr. Jose Palazzo Moreira de Oliveira	Prof. Dr. Jan Vanthienen
Prof. Dr. Yoshinori Hara	Prof. Dr. Leszek Maciaszek	Prof. Dr. Nineta Polemi	Prof. Dr. Jelena Zdravkovic
Prof. Dr. Knut Hinkelmann	Dr. Hisashi Masuda	Prof. Dr. Claudia Pons	Prof. Dr. Heinz Zülligshoven

OMLAB Modelling Method Engineering Framework

NEMO 2015

University of Vienna, Austria
20th - 31st of July 2015

The PARTICIPANTS

Maxim Alkhlou

Hery Andriankaja

Damiano Nunzio Arena

Nikolaos Argyropoulos

Dominik Augenstein

Katarzyna Moc

Alexandra-Maria Negoescu

Xuesong Peng

Giovanni Quattrocchi

Suneth Ranasinghe

Arne Bergmann

Martin Bergner

Alexander Bock

Clemens Böhm

Yeongbok Choe

Murat Salmanoğlu

Philipp Salzmann

Vincenzo Sciacca

Benjamin Ternes

Dimitrios Tosidis

Woorim Choi

Mateusz Czerniecki

Alexander Derkinderen

Vladimir Dimitrieski

Sara D'Onofrio

Marvin Triebel

Claudia Vannucchi

Arthur Vetter

Anna Widenmaier

Paula Zalhan

Andreea Dumitrescu

Markus Fischer

Charlotte Gils

Iulia Cristina Hatiegan

Ebuka Emmanuel Ibeanusi

Ahson Javaid

Amna Javed

Cornelia Jetzinger

Nour Jnoub

Konrad Jurk

Eleni Maria Kalogeraki

Patrik König

Sabrina Kurjakovic

Martin Latzenhofer

Sung Hyeon Lee

Nikos Lykousas

Nishtha Madaan

Alexandru Razvan Manescu

Francesco Marconi

Giovanni Meroni

<https://nemo.omilab.org/2015/>

Participants: 50

Nationalities: 18

Institutions: 25

Countries: 15

3rd Edition - NEMO 2016 Summer School

3rd Edition in the NEMO Summer School Series
**NEXT GENERATION ENTERPRISE MODELLING
 IN THE AGE OF INTERNET OF THINGS**
 July 18th - July 29th, 2016 - University of Vienna, Austria
<http://nemo.omilab.org/2016/>

CALL FOR PARTICIPATION

NEMO Summer School Series

The NEMO summer schools focus on the conceptualization, design, and implementation of Next Generation Enterprise Modelling Methods. In today's enterprises, modelling methods are widely used on every level and they are mostly supported by modelling tools. These tools ease the design of machine-processable models and provide facility services, e.g. for accessing, exchanging and persistently storing meta-models and models, for applying algorithms and querying model contents. Additionally they enhance the value of models as organisational knowledge platforms. Modelling tools and platforms which support domain specific methods need to provide user interaction functionalities and enable management capabilities for the execution environment in addition to the modelling method design and implementation.

Framework and Topics

The generic modelling method framework proposed by Karagiannis and Kihna (2001) comprises all the necessary ingredients for the conceptualization, i.e. early development and prototyping phases of modelling tools for domain specific modelling methods.

The framework addresses

- modelling languages - syntax, semantic and notation,
- modelling procedures, and
- processing based on their mechanisms and algorithms.

The summer school provides a highly-interactive experimental environment, where students and teachers focus on modelling addressing especially

- Foundations of Conceptual Modelling
- Technologies for Conceptual Modelling
- Application Domains
- Cross-cutting Issues.

Contributing Lecturers and Institutions*

Prof. Dr. Doo-Hwan Bae, Korea	Prof. Dr. Knut Hinkelmann, Switzerland	Prof. Dr. Oscar Pastor, Spain
Prof. Dr. Xavier Boucher, France	Ass. Prof. Dr. Manfred Jeusfeld, Sweden	Prof. Dr. Andrea Polini, Italy
Ass. Prof. Dr. Robert Buchmann, Romania	Prof. Dr. Dimitris Karagiannis, Austria	Prof. Dr. Barbara Re, Italy
Prof. Dr. Luis Camarinha-Matos, Portugal	Prof. Dr. Evangelia Kawalki, Greece	Prof. Dr. Peter Reimann, Australia
Prof. Dr. Jin-Young Choi, Korea	Prof. Dr. Marite Kirikova, Latvia	Prof. Dr. Wolfgang Reissig, Germany
Prof. Dr. Elisabetta Di Nitto, Italy	Prof. Dr. Dimitris Kiritsis, Switzerland	Prof. Dr. Matti Rossi, Finland
Prof. Dr. Hans-Georg Fill, Austria	Prof. Dr. Kiyoshi Kobayashi, Japan	Prof. Dr. Nick Roussopoulos, USA
Prof. Dr. Xavier Franch, Spain	Prof. Dr. John Krogstad, Norway	Prof. Dr. Bernhard Thalheim, Germany
Prof. Dr. Ulrich Frank, Germany	Prof. Dr. Moon Kun Lee, Korea	Prof. Dr. Jan Vanthienen, Belgium
Ass. Prof. Dr. Kelly Johany Garces Pernet, Colombia	Prof. Dr. Pericles Loucopoulos, UK	Prof. Dr. Frank Wolff, Germany
Prof. Dr. Martin Güntz, Switzerland	Ass. Prof. Dr. Hisashi Masuda, Japan	Prof. Dr. Eric Yu, Canada
Prof. Dr. Wilfried Grossmann, Austria	Prof. Dr. Heinrich C. Mayr, Austria	Mr. John Zachmann, USA
Prof. Dr. Yoshinori Hara, Japan	Prof. Dr. Haris Mouratidis, UK	Prof. Dr. Helena Zdravkovic, Sweden
Prof. Dr. Igor Hawryszewicz, Australia	Prof. Dr. Andreas Oberweis, Germany	Prof. Dr. Heinz Züllighoven, Germany

Lead Institutions and Organizers:

NEMO 2016

University of Vienna, Austria
 18th - 29th of July 2016

The PARTICIPANTS

Novia Indriaty Admodisastro

Ayed Alwadain

Jason Anagnostopoulos

Athanasios Basios

Swante Brechler

Christian Muck

David Naranjo

Damir Nesic

Boon Yaik Ooi

Mohd Azam Osman

Mohamad Firdaus Che Abdul Rani

Wai Khuen Cheng

Sangje Cho

Tomasz Chojnacki

Daniel-Cristian Craciunean

Vik Pant

Eleni Vasiliki Papathanasiou

Panos Pappas

Maria Piacha

Tiago Prince Sales

Sergio Cuenca

Jamilah Din

Shir Dotan

Tamara Drucks

Tarek Elmadany

Laleh Rafati

Adam Sagaev

George Sanidas

Shanny Shohet

JunSup Song

Tamer Emara

Marcelo Esperguel Sandoval

Jan Fauser

Jingyuan Feng

Andreas Fritsch

Evellin Cristine Souza Cardoso

Lijun Sun

Ahamad Tajudin Khader

Daniel Töpel

Georgios Tsilikas

Daphne Georgiou

Mustafa Ghani

Ana-Maria Ghiran

Ricardo Giuliani Martini

Christian Gläser

Markus Unger

Velitchko Valkov

Aparna Vegendla

Antonius Verhoeven

Mark-Philipp Wolfger

Mitja Gradišnik

Michele Guerriero

Didem Gürdür

Julia Kaidalova

Andreas Kanellos

Poh Lee Wong

Tom Yanovich

Arezoo Khatibi

Prodromos Kolyvakis

SungHyeon Lee

Donatas Mazeika

Abderrahmane Moujahid

internationality

community

networking

multi-cultural

knowledge exchange

cooperation

<https://nemo.omilab.org/2016/>

🎓 Participants: 64

📍 Nationalities: 27

🏛️ Institutions: 42

🌐 Countries: 25

shared values

collaboration

<https://nemo.omilab.org/2017/>

🎓 Participants: 58

📍 Nationalities: 27

🏛️ Institutions: 36

🌐 Countries: 24

experience

support

community

4th Edition - NEMO 2017 Summer School

4th Edition in the NEMO Summer School Series

NEXT GENERATION ENTERPRISE MODELLING IN THE AGE OF INTERNET OF THINGS

July 17th - July 28th, 2017 - University of Vienna, Austria
<http://nemo.omlab.org/>

CALL FOR PARTICIPATION

NEMO Summer School Series

The NEMO summer schools focus on the conceptualization, design, and implementation of Next Generation Enterprise Modelling Methods. In today's enterprises, modelling methods are widely used on every level and they are mostly supported by modelling tools. These tools ease the design of machine-processable models and provide facility services, e.g. for accessing, exchanging and persistently storing meta-models and models, for applying algorithms and querying model contents. Additionally they enhance the value of models as organisational knowledge platform.

Framework and Topics

The generic modelling method framework proposed by Karagiannis and Kühn (2011) comprises all the necessary ingredients for the conceptualization, i.e. early development and prototyping phases of modelling tools for domain specific modelling methods. Prototypical tool implementations applying the framework are available in the book „Domain-Specific Conceptual Modelling: Concepts, Methods and Tools“ (2016, Springer).

The framework addresses

- modelling languages - syntax, semantic and notation,
- modelling procedures, and
- processing based on their mechanisms and algorithms.

The summer school provides a highly-interactive experimental environment, where students and teachers focus on modelling addressing especially

- Foundations of Conceptual Modelling
- Technologies for Conceptual Modelling
- Application Domains
- Cross-cutting Issues.

Contributing Lecturers and Institutions

Prof. Dr. Doo-Hwan Bae, Korea	Prof. Dr. Dimitris Karagiannis, Austria	Prof. Dr. Andrea Polini, Italy
Prof. Dr. Xavier Boucher, France	Prof. Dr. Evangelia Kawaiki, Greece	Prof. Dr. Barbara Re, Italy
Asst. Prof. Dr. Robert Buchmann, Romania	Prof. Dr. Marite Kirikova, Latvia	Prof. Dr. Peter Reimann, Australia
Prof. Dr. Luis Camarinho-Matos, Portugal	Prof. Dr. Dimitris Kiriakis, Switzerland	Prof. Dr. Wolfgang Reisp, Germany
Prof. Dr. Jin-Young Choi, Korea	Prof. Dr. Kiyoshi Kobayashi, Japan	Prof. Dr. Matti Rossi, Finland
Prof. Dr. Elisabetta di Nitto, Italy	Prof. Dr. John Krogtstie, Norway	Prof. Dr. Nick Rousopoulos, USA
Prof. Dr. Hans-Georg Fill, Austria	Prof. Dr. Moon Kun Lee, Korea	Prof. Dr. Bernhard Rumpe, Germany
Prof. Dr. Ulrich Frank, Germany	Prof. Dr. Pericles Loucopoulos, UK	Prof. Dr. Bernhard Thalheim, Germany
Asst. Prof. Dr. Kelly J Garces Permett, Colombia	Asst. Prof. Dr. Hisashi Masuda, Japan	Prof. Dr. Jan Vanthienen, Belgium
Prof. Dr. Wilfried Grossmann, Austria	Prof. Dr. Heinrich C. Mayr, Austria	Prof. Dr. Frank Wolf, Germany
Prof. Dr. Yoshinori Hara, Japan	Prof. Dr. Haris Mouratidis, UK	Prof. Dr. Eric Yu, Canada
Prof. Dr. Igor Hawryszkiewicz, Australia	Prof. Dr. John Mylopoulos, Canada	Mr. John Zachman, USA
Prof. Dr. Knut Hinkelmann, Switzerland	Prof. Dr. Andreas Oberweis, Germany	Prof. Dr. Jelena Zdravkovic, Sweden
Asst. Prof. Dr. Manfred Jeusfeld, Sweden	Prof. Dr. Oscar Pastor, Spain	Prof. Dr. Heinz Züllighoven, Germany

Participating Institutions and Organizers:

NEMO 2017

University of Vienna, Austria
 17th - 28th of July 2017

The PARTICIPANTS

Afef Awadid

Workneh Yilma Ayele

Young-Min Baek

Suraj Bhattarai

Rainara Carvalho

Michiel Ocula

Raphaël Oger

Bogdan Okresa Duric

Martha Orellano

Martin Paczona

Ana Karina Castolo

Chia-Hsuan Chang

Kuan-Lin Chen

Mihai Cinpoeru

Ana Elena Cristina

Horatiu Constantin Palade

Andrei Pocora

Mirona Ana-Maria Popescu

Foivos Psarommatis Giannakopoulos

Maryam Rahmani

Victoria Döller

Marko Flajšek

Marco Franceschetti

Manon Froger

Zacharenia Garofalaki

Sabina Rako

Roberto Sala

Quentin Schoen

Petar Šestak

Haiyang Shi

Parisa Ghazi

Simona Gheorghe

Kanwal Daud Gill

Kristens Gudfinnsson

Philipp Hamann

Junsup Song

Emil Tochev

Yuri Variat

Vasilis Vasilakopoulos

Mark von Dewitz

Alisa Harkai

Luis Hernández

Truong Quang Huy

Ahson Javaid

Jaka Jereb

Zheng Jiang

Themelis Kalomirois

Zakariya Kamagaté

Miroslav Kubelskiy

Irina Levin

Paola Mejía Domenzain

Lukas Miklautz

Rebeca Motta

Sina Namaki Araghi

Marco Nardello

The PARTICIPANTS

Souad Amghar

Donald Baldwin

Parthena Basina

Viviana Bastidas

Chung-Chieh Chin

Eva Petitdemange

Omkar Salunkhe

Christine Schruffer

Anna Sumereder

Elena-Madalina Talpos

Görkem Çoklar

Galina Dimitrova

Paul Arthur Dreyfus

Matthias Ehrendorfer

Imane Essebaa

Bethaina Touijer

YiHang Tsai

Marko Vještica

Anthony Wensley

Michela Zambetti

Omar Ezzat

Christian Fischer-Pauzenberger

Jonas Geelhaar

Carmen Gog

Delphine Guillon

Liwen Zhang

Yaxian Zhou

Yanling Zhuang

Amir Haj-Bolouri

Tokio Kawakami

Ibrahim Koura

Georgios Koutsopoulos

Georgios Kyriazidis

Yosra Lassoued

Jiayao Li

Tai Tan Mai

Pawel Malik

Luka Markovic

Alexandru Matei

Annette Mavelleue

Hassan Mir

Silviu Miroslav

Cristina Maria Modranga

Florin Ionut Munteanu

Lukas Netz

Małgorzata Oles

Claudia Paciarotti

Sunghwan Park

<https://nemo.omilab.org/2018/>

Participants: 47

Nationalities: 25

Institutions: 37

Countries: 21

6th Edition - NEMO 2019 Summer School

6th Edition
NEMO SUMMER SCHOOL SERIES
 University of Vienna
<http://nemo.omlab.org/>

July 15 - 26 2019

NEXT GENERATION ENTERPRISE MODELLING IN THE DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION AGE

CALL FOR PARTICIPATION

NEMO Summer School Series

The NEMO summer schools focus on the conceptualization, design, and implementation of Next Generation Enterprise Modelling Methods. In today's enterprises, modelling methods are widely used on every level and they are mostly supported by modelling tools. These tools ease the design of machine-processable models and provide facility services, e.g. for accessing, exchanging and persistently storing meta-models and models, for applying algorithms and querying model contents. Additionally they enhance the value of models as organisational knowledge platforms.

Framework and Topics

The generic modelling method framework proposed by Karagiannis and Kühn (2001) comprises all the necessary ingredients for the conceptualization, i.e. early development and prototyping phases of modelling tools for domain specific modelling methods. Prototypical tool implementations applying the framework are available in the book „Domain-Specific Conceptual Modelling: Concepts, Methods and Tools“ (2016, Springer).

The framework addresses
 (a) modelling languages - syntax, semantic and notation,
 (b) modelling procedures, and
 (c) processing based on their mechanisms and algorithms.

OMLAB Modelling Method Engineering Framework

The summer school provides a highly-interactive experimental environment, where students and teachers focus on modelling addressing especially

- Foundations of Conceptual Modelling
- Technologies for Conceptual Modelling
- Application Domains
- Cross-cutting Issues.

Disclaimer: This project has been funded with support from the European Commission. This publication reflects the views only of the author, and the Commission cannot be held responsible for any use that may be made of the information contained therein.

6th Edition
NEMO SUMMER SCHOOL SERIES
 nemo.omlab.org

Vienna 15 - 26 July 2019

NEXT GENERATION ENTERPRISE MODELLING IN THE DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION AGE

universität wien OMLAB® Erasmus+

Contributing Institutions & Sponsors 2014 - 2018

Disclaimer: This project has been funded with support from the European Commission. This publication reflects the views only of the author, and the Commission cannot be held responsible for any use that may be made of the information contained therein.

NEMO 2019

University of Vienna, Austria
 15th - 26th of July 2019

Amine Abbad Andaloussi

Mahwish Anwar

Octavian-Isaia Baltas

Zelalem Mihret Belay

Anubhav Bhardwaj

Alexandru Calinescu

Mathias Cammerlander

Philip Cammin

Sunwoo Cho

Vipin Deval

Abhishek Dixit

Alexandru Dragan

Runtian Feng

Axel Germond

Panagiotis Gkotsiopoulos

Michelle Hounghé

Sangwon Hyun

Lijo Johny

Kaito Koike

Juan Manuel Lagos Obando

Kwanho Lee

Sebastian Macht

Yolanda Mbanguzi

Devid Montecchiari

Maria Muntean

Andres Camilo Murillo Coba

Cristina-Claudia Osman

Charuta Pande

Jinwoo Park

Jacques Pasquier

Tomislav Peharda

Jorge Puente

Claudia Elizabeth Roessing Rocha

Nelson Marcelo Romero Aquino

Donya Rooein

The PARTICIPANTS

Alexandre Sarazin

Clemens Schreiber

Selina Athesa Schüler

Eleni Seralidou

Maja Spahic-Bogdanovic

Nathalie Spicher

Monika Tenšić

Rafika Thabet

Duong Thi Binh An

Sanaa Tiss

Philipp Url

Iulia Vaidian

Pablo Valenzuela

Charlotte Verbruggen

Abhijay Vuyyuru

Anna Wolff

Noé Mathieu Wysshaar

Jan Zadrozny

<https://nemo.omilab.org/2019/>

NEMO 2020 Summer School

NEMO
2020

Unfortunately couldn't take place ...due to the pandemic!

On pause ...due to Covid-19!

7th Edition - NEMO 2021 Summer School

7th Edition
NEMO SUMMER SCHOOL SERIES
 Vienna 19 - 30 July 2021
BECOME A DIGITAL LEADER!
 nemo.omlab.org

CALL FOR PARTICIPATION

NEMO Summer School Series
 The NEMO summer schools focus on the design and implementation of Enterprise Digital Twins and Ecosystems based on conceptual modelling methods. They enable the design of semantically rich diagrammatic models that are both human-understandable and machine-processable, while providing services for analyzing models and interoperating with open digital environments. Conceptual models can thus be used as the knowledge platform of an organization and their value can be co-created by flexible collaboration between digital engineers and stakeholders.

Join the NEMO Summer School to learn how conceptual modelling supports innovation, design and engineering for digital business ecosystems!

Working in and for digitized organizations where smart devices, digital artefacts, robots, data streams and connectivity are ubiquitous, you will be faced with challenges pertaining to human resources, process lifecycles, business or regulatory rules. NEMO provides a vertical overview across different application domains to prepare you for all dimensions of digitization.

Framework and Topics
 The Digital Innovation environment of OMLAB enables experimentation and training for both conceptualization and engineering activities. Stakeholders from a multi-disciplinary background are supported to develop innovative ideas as digital business models, to materialize them in proofs-of-concept and to evaluate their feasibility in a laboratory setting.

Previous Editions

OMLAB NPO
 Vision: an active global community for conceptual modelling that benefits from open artefacts.
 Openness: to all those interested, either as individuals or as institutions. It acts as an ecosystem where participants can bring in ideas related to conceptual modelling and engage in the exploration process.
 Laboratories: dedicated research and experimentation spaces for modelling method engineering equipped with tools to explore method creation and design, experiment with method engineering and deploy digital innovation.
 Benefits: dialogue between digital innovators and digital engineers, with amplification instruments which leverage the impact of the activities performed.

NEMO 2021

ONLINE
 19th - 30th of July 2021

The one and only ONLINE edition...due to the pandemic!

The PARTICIPANTS

Chayma Abid

Larbi Afif

Mahmoud Mohamed Ibrahim Ahmed

Ajeeragani

Yazeed Al Zahrani

Juan De Antón Heredero

Galina Dimitrova

Konstantinos Douloudis

Vaidotas Drungilas

Souha El Wejhani

Narjis Almawlawi

Orlando Amaral Cejas

Alexis Amaye

Paul-Valer Andrei

Maria Eftychia Angelaki

Dorsaf Etlili

George Fatouros

Arianna Fedeli

Marko Flajsek

Martin Forell

Sotiris Angelis

Rushan Arshad

Virendra Ashiwai

Sara Baghaei

Issam Bahloul

Demian Frister

Mattia Galimberti

Marwa Gannoun

Mohamed Gharbi

Yasaman Gheidar

Safa Bahri

Donald Baldwin

Kazeem Balogun

Parthena Basina

Viviana Bastidas

Sebastian Gottschalk

Steven Gross

Alicja Gudanowska

César Arturo Guerra García

Latifa Guesmi

Fatima Bayloun

Oussema Ben Amara

Taha Ben Dhia

Hatem Ben Sta

Romain Ben Taleb

Mehdi Hadj Sassi

Zeineb Hajji

Felix Härer

Natalia Hartono

Yaraslava Herasimuk

Fiodor Bodnar

Karsten Böhm

Stylianios Bourmpoulas

Ramzi Bouzaienne

Amina Brahem

Jorge Hernandez

Gabriel Hogan

Larisa Hrustek

Jannik Imbery

Loussaief Imen

Kai Cao

Thibaut Cerabona

Mohamad Firdaus
Che Abdul Rani

Andrei Chis

Andrei Razvan Corlaci

Asrul Ismail

Olalekan Isola

Teodora Ispas

Elham Jelodari Mamaghani

Jaka Jereb

The PARTICIPANTS

Kaiwen Jiang

Sayooj Aby Jose

Marina Jurcic

Mantas Jurgelaitis

Yusmadi Yah Jusoh

Mark Mulder

Brian Ndlovu

Maryna Nehrey

Sherilynn Siew Fong Ngerng

Rene Noel

Dorothea Kam

Johanna Yik-Han Kam

Ioannis Kasionis

Meriem Kasmi

John Paul Kasse

Oluniyi Ogunbiyi

Bogdan Okresa Duric

Italo Oliveira

Khaled Omrane

Mesli Ouissem

Fadime Kaya

Tshifhiwa Kgalema

Kamel Khedhiri

Daniel Kiesenhofer

Goo-Young Kim

Oyepeju Oyekola

Zeynep Ozturk Yurt

Dan Palade

Anna Pamula

Malgorzata Pankowska

Dimitrios Kotsifakos

Noel Koutlis

Filippos Dimitrios Ktistakis

Ana Kutnjak

Mustapha Labreche

Michail Pantelelis

Randy Paredis

Nicola Pedot

Tatiana Poletaeva

Sabina Rako

Matheus Ladeira Boechat Lemos

Juan Lagos

Fatima Laiche

Paola Lara Machado

Safa Lasmar

Lassaad Sahli

Mehdi Sajadieh

Sabbir Muhammad Saleh

Theodoros Samios

Giovanna Sampaio

Steven Leego

Mengyang Li

Chuangtao Ma

Gang Ma

Alexandru Matei

Balša Šarenac

Ioannis Sarlis

Ee Ling Saw

Florian Schierlinger-Brandmayr

David Schmalzing

Houda Mezrigui

Reza Mohammadi

Nafe Moradkhani

Jose Mosquera

Saradhi Motamarri

Clemens Schreiber

Selina Schüler

Eleni Seralidou

Fatemeh Shiri

Seyed Hossein Siadat

The PARTICIPANTS

Maria Siapera

Julia Siderska

Fatima-Zahrae Sifi

Ivana Sitaric

Tarek Skouti

Ensi Smajli

Mohamed Adnen Souaia

Maja Spahic-Bogdanovic

Murali Sridharan

Caramon Stanley

Stavros Stavridis

Anna Sumereder

Anna Szymczak

Chuyingjie Tang

Bethaina Touijer

Chen Hsi Tsai

Nazanin Vafaei

Vishnu Varthan

Romel Aldair Vazquez Molina

Alvaro Mario Veizaga Campero

Rosa Velasquez Rojas

Marco Venuta

Noella Verschuren

Alexander Völz

Christian Vorbohle

Marwa Walha

Emily Weidt

Zishi Wu

Selim Yasar

Ilbay Yavuz

Chong Zhi Lin

Marina Zubova

Danial Mohammadi Amlashi

<https://nemo.omilab.org/2021/>

Participants: 252

Nationalities: 66

Institutions: 122

Countries: 45

LinkedIn Testimonials

internationality

"It was an incredible experience."

Camilo #NEMO2019

networking

multi-cultural

"I really enjoyed the multi-cultural environment and the opportunity to work with peers and experts from different backgrounds."

Christian #NEMO2022

cooperation

"The experience was not just intellectually stimulating but also culturally enriching."

Ramona #NEMO2023

"Inspiring, instructive and future-changing."

Marianne #NEMO2022

"It was a fantastic opportunity to gain new insights and skills."

George #NEMO2023

"I met many new good friends and experts from all over the world. In all, it was a memorable and rewarding experience."

Novia #NEMO2016

share

"It was a great experience in the beautiful city of Vienna."

Fabian #NEMO2023

colla

"I am incredibly grateful for this experience, for all the things I learned and all the awesome people I met."

Alisa #NEMO2023

experience

"These two weeks were filled with immersive learning experiences, valuable training, and fruitful networking sessions."

Mehran #NEMO2023

community

8th Edition - NEMO 2022 Summer School

8th Edition
NEMO SUMMER SCHOOL SERIES
 nemo.omlab.org

Vienna
 11 - 22 July
 2022

BECOME A DIGITAL LEADER!

CALL FOR PARTICIPATION

universität wien | Erasmus+

NEMO Summer School Series

The NEMO summer schools focus on the design and implementation of Enterprise Digital Twins and Ecosystems based on conceptual modelling methods. They enable the design of semantically rich diagrammatic models that are both human-understandable and machine-processable, while providing services for analyzing models and interoperating with open digital environments. Conceptual models can thus be used as the knowledge platform of an organization and their value can be co-created by flexible collaboration between digital engineers and stakeholders.

Join the NEMO Summer School to learn how conceptual modelling supports innovation, design and engineering for digital business ecosystems!

Working in and for digitized organizations where smart devices, digital artefacts, robots, data streams and connectivity are ubiquitous, you will be faced with challenges pertaining to human resources, process lifecycles, business or regulatory rules. NEMO provides a vertical overview across different application domains to prepare you for all dimensions of digitization.

Framework and Topics

The Digital Innovation environment of OMLAB enables experimentation and training for both conceptualization and engineering activities. Stakeholders from a multi-disciplinary background are supported to develop innovative ideas as digital business models, to materialize them in proofs-of-concept and to evaluate their feasibility in a laboratory setting.

Previous Editions

OMLAB NPO

OMLAB
www.omlab.org

Vision: an active global community for conceptual modelling that benefits from open artefacts.

Openness: to all those interested, either as individuals or as institutions. It acts as an ecosystem where participants can bring in ideas related to conceptual modelling and engage in the exploration process.

Laboratories: dedicated research and experimentation spaces for modelling method engineering equipped with tools to explore method creation and design, experiment with method engineering and deploy digital innovation.

Benefits: dialogue between digital innovators and digital engineers, with amplification instruments which leverage the impact of the activities performed.

Approach: Conceptual Modelling, Metamodeling, Digital Twins

Technology: ADDox, Olive, BEE-UP, CoChaCo, Visual Studio

Digital Innovation Environment of OMLAB

The summer school provides a highly interactive experimental environment, where students and teachers focus on conceptual modelling for digital innovation ecosystems, covering topics such as:

- Foundations of Conceptual Modelling
- „Smart Models“ for humans and machines
- Concepts and technologies for Digital Ecosystems
- Digital Design Thinking
- Enterprise Digital Twins
- Cross-Cutting Issues

NEMO 2022

University of Vienna, Austria
 11th - 22th of July 2022

Rushan Arshad

Anojan Arunasalam

Kazeem Balogun

Sam Ban

Pradipta Banerjee

Hatem Ben Sta

Johan Bergelin

Meehyun Cho

Arianna Fedeli

Enxhi Ferko

Alexandru Filipescu

Marius-Lucian Gal

Ayush Goyal

Michal Halaška

Malte Heithoff

Franziska Selina Hollauf Hollauf

Mohammad Mustafa Ibrahimy

Sania Khan

Hansu Kim

Foteini Kontonika

Milan Kostic

Steven Leego

Paola Lara Machado

Mehran Majidian Eidgahi

Mariza Maliqi

David A. Manrique Negrin

Roland Paul Moraru

Hossain Muhammad Muctadir

Hadi Nowandish

Christian Orlowski

Lizanne Ottiger

Oyepeju Oyekola

Zeynep Ozturk Yurt

Rikardo Protrka

Anshul Rani

The PARTICIPANTS

Matthias Reichmann

Paul Savignac

Florian Schierlinger-Brandmayr

Marianne Schnellmann

Yongjun Shin

Natascha Sigle

Milica Škembarević

Tarek Skouti

Maja Spahic-Bogdanovic

Julian Christopher Steiner

Daniel Chen Hsi Tsai

Montijn van de Ven

Seline Wenger

Zishi Wu

Ehsan Yadegari

Yao Yao

<https://nemo.omilab.org/2022/>

Participants: 51

Nationalities: 29

Institutions: 29

Countries: 19

9th Edition - NEMO 2023 Summer School

9th Edition
NEMO SUMMER SCHOOL SERIES
 nemo.omlab.org

Vienna
 17 - 28 July
 2023

BECOME A DIGITAL LEADER!

CALL FOR PARTICIPATION

Erasmus+

NEMO Summer School Series

The NEMO summer schools focus on the design and implementation of Enterprise Digital Twins and Ecosystems based on conceptual modelling methods. They enable the design of semantically rich diagrammatic models that are both human-understandable and machine-processable, while providing services for analyzing models and interpreting with open digital environments. Conceptual models can thus be used as the knowledge platform of an organization and their value can be co-created by flexible collaboration between digital engineers and stakeholders.

Join the NEMO Summer School to learn how conceptual modelling supports innovation, design and engineering for digital business ecosystems!

Working in and for digitized organizations where smart devices, digital artefacts, robots, data streams and connectivity are ubiquitous, you will be faced with challenges pertaining to human resources, process lifecycles, business or regulatory rules. NEMO provides a vertical overview across different application domains to prepare you for all dimensions of digitization.

Framework and Topics

The Digital Innovation environment of OMLAB enables experimentation and training for both conceptualization and engineering activities. Stakeholders from a multi-disciplinary background are supported to develop innovative ideas as digital business models, to materialize them in proofs-of-concept and to evaluate their feasibility in a laboratory setting.

OMILAB NPO

OMLAB
www.omlab.org

Vision: an active global community for conceptual modelling that benefits from open artefacts.

Openness: to all those interested, either as individuals or as institutions. It acts as an ecosystem where participants can bring in ideas related to conceptual modelling and engage in the exploration process.

Laboratories: dedicated research and experimentation spaces for modelling method engineering equipped with tools to explore method creation and design, experiment with method engineering and deploy digital innovation.

Benefits: dialogue between digital innovators and digital engineers, with amplification instruments which leverage the impact of the activities performed.

Digital Innovation Environment of OMLAB

The summer school provides a highly interactive experimental environment, where students and teachers focus on conceptual modelling for digital innovation ecosystems, covering topics such as:

- Foundations of Conceptual Modelling
- "Smart Models" for humans and machines
- Concepts and technologies for Digital Ecosystems
- Digital Design Thinking
- Enterprise Digital Twins
- Cross-Cutting Issues

NEMO 2023

University of Vienna, Austria
 17th - 28th of July 2023

The PARTICIPANTS

Omar Aitoulghazi

Sofana Alfuhaid

Ahmad Almaarif

Nedo Alexander Bartels

Eduard Bondarev

Efstathios Trantalis

Iva Vasic

Gustavo Vieira

Henry Webler

Nipuna Hiranya Weeratunge

Stylianos Bourmpoulis

Elena Cascavilla

Yun-Chi Chang

Tomasz Eisenbardt

Ramona Elali

Mairita Zake

Gennaro Zanfardino

Paraskevi-Chrysovalantou Zangogianni

Mehran Farkhondeh

George Victor Gall

Khan Mohammad Habibullah

Alexandra Hancu

Rafael Humann Petry

Predrag Imšić

Juha-Pekka Joutsenlahti

Shervin Kakhoda Ahmadi

Josias Knöppler

Snježana Križanić

Branko Krsmanović

Darius Langsdorf

Alisa Lorenz

Ilija Maslov

Seydeh Fatemeh Mir Bagheri Marvili

Andrei Pavel

Rostislav Iša

Fabian Rybinski

Vinesh Thiruchelvam

Miroslav Tomić

<https://nemo.omilab.org/2023/>

10th Edition - NEMO 2024 Summer School

10th Edition
NEMO SUMMER SCHOOL SERIES
 Vienna 15 - 26 July 2024
BECOME A DIGITAL LEADER!
 nemo.omlab.org

CALL FOR PARTICIPATION

universität wien Erasmus+

NEMO Summer School Series

The NEMO summer schools focus on the design and implementation of Enterprise Digital Twins and Ecosystems based on conceptual modelling methods. They enable the design of semantically rich diagrammatic models that are both human-understandable and machine-processable, while providing services for analyzing models and interoperating with open digital environments. Conceptual models can thus be used as the knowledge platform of an organization and their value can be co-created by flexible collaboration between digital engineers and stakeholders.

Join the NEMO Summer School to learn how conceptual modelling supports innovation, design and engineering for digital business ecosystems!

Working in and for digitized organizations where smart devices, digital artefacts, robots, data streams and connectivity are ubiquitous, you will be faced with challenges pertaining to human resources, process lifecycles, business or regulatory rules. NEMO provides a vertical overview across different application domains to prepare you for all dimensions of digitization.

Framework and Topics

The Digital Innovation environment of OMLAB enables experimentation and training for both conceptualization and engineering activities. Stakeholders from a multi-disciplinary background are supported to develop innovative ideas as digital business models, to materialize them in proofs-of-concept and to evaluate their feasibility in a laboratory setting.

Approach: Conceptual Modelling, Metamodeling, Digital Twins

Technology: ADOxx, Olive, BEE-UP, CoChaCo, Visual Studio

Digital Innovation Environment of OMLAB

The summer school provides a highly interactive experimental environment, where students and teachers focus on conceptual modelling for digital innovation ecosystems, covering topics such as:

- Foundations of Conceptual Modelling
- „Smart Models“ for humans and machines
- Concepts and technologies for Digital Ecosystems
- Digital Design Thinking
- Enterprise Digital Twins
- Cross-Cutting Issues

Previous Editions

10th Edition
NEMO SUMMER SCHOOL SERIES
 Vienna 15 - 26 July 2024
 Become a digital leader!
 Learn CONCEPTUAL MODELLING to innovate, design and engineer digital ecosystems
 nemo.omlab.org

universität wien OMLAB[®] Erasmus+

Build digital twins of the future!

Contributing Institutions & Sponsors

NEMO 2024

University of Vienna, Austria
 15th - 26th of July 2024

The PARTICIPANTS

Faima Abbasi

Nur Arifin Akbar

Lalla Hasnae Alaoui

Pierre Averty

Kamal Benramdane

Aneta Biernikowicz

Fuad Budagov

Kyra Buhlmann

Michael Capper

Axel Christfort

Claudia Negri Ribalta

Tomasz Parys

Andrei Pătrăușanu

Darmin Poturovic

Sangeetha-Rose Puthanveetil

Ebrar Dauti

Rahool Dembani

Elena Dergalina

Hans-Rudolf Dimmler

Marija Đukić

Bennet Puthuparambil

Abdul Raheem

Kishan Rajah

Miguel de Jesus Ramirez Cadena

Isabel Reuter

Patrick Eugster

Matteo Falconi

Alexandru Ganea

Paula-Manuela Giurgiu

Chenxue Huang

Jeddy Shahriar

Karthickeshwar Shankaravelu

Daria Sopotcko

Ivan Spajić

Johanna Steinbach

Olga Jejić

Elizaveta Kariavkina

Jesse Katende

Theodore Kindong

Sana Kiran

Stefan Stevanovic

Alexander Tampier

Răzvan Constantin Țoșhe

Ana Lucia Tula

Joep van Wanrooij

Veronika Kostrouchová

Tejas Kotha

Yaksh Kumar

Aritha Kumarasinghe

Joyce David Martin

Jingyang Wang

Shudan Yang

Natalí Maza

Kunruthai Meechang

Kristina Mircetic

Gabriel Mugabe Nzarama

Ioana Nagit

<https://nemo.omilab.org/2024/>

🎓 Participants: 57

📍 Nationalities: 32

🏛️ Institutions: 41

🌐 Countries: 22

IMPRESSIONS

Danial Mohammadi Amlashi

Nikola Babic

Dominik Bork

Patrik Burzynski

Victoria Döller

Simon Doppler

David Götzing

Iulia Cristina Hatiegan

Kira Kinateder

Vimal Kunnummel

Daniel Lexian

Verena Madlberger-Kleinschmid

Antonia Mihelleyes

Elena -Teodora Miron

Christian Muck

Thank you for 10 great years!

To the participants, the professors, the industry experts, the sponsors and the team - everyone who made the NEMO Summer School an unforgettable experience!

It was great to meet all of you and we are proud to see how much the worldwide NEMO Alumni Community has grown over the years.

We hope you can look back at your NEMO experience with fond memories and valuable learnings for both your professional and personal growth.

Now, we are excited for the next step in the NEMO journey - we hope to reconnect with you along the way!

Sincerely,
the NEMO Team

NEMO Team *over the years*

Antonia Patzak

Benedikt Pittl

Barbara Reiter

Franz Staffel

Hannah Staffel

Nikolaos Tantouris

Valentina Tessa

Mira Tjoa

Wilfrid Utz

Ayda Uzel

Iulia Vaidian

Niksa Visic

Alexander Völz

Karlheinz Wachauer

Michael Walch

Iulia Vaidian
OMiLAB NPO
events@omilab.org

- NEMOSummerSchool
- openmodelslaboratory
- omilabnpo
- omilab
- OMiLAB NPO
- OMiLAB

NEMO ALUMNI Community

<https://nemo.omilab.org/alumni>

Join the NEMO Alumni Community on LinkedIn!

The NEMO Community continues to grow, through the NEMO Innovation Camp Series!